

***Chacolíes*: Light Wines and Strong Identities in North-West Spain and South America**

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Abstract

Chacolí is the name of a fascinating family of light wines that was born in Northwest Spain at the turn of the 16th century and whose American branch dates back to the end of the 18th or the beginning of the 19th. *Chacolíes* have been historically produced in Northwest Spain (Cantabria, Basqueland, Navarre and Burgos), and Chile and Argentina (Rio Negro).

Those from Basqueland are currently sold under three Protected Denomination of Origin: *Getariako Txakolina* (1989), *Bizkaiko Txakolina* (1994) and *Arabako Txakolina* (2001). In this synthetic panorama, we first question the complex notion of “*chacolí*”, taking into account its etymology. We show that the most probable hypotheses are those that link “*chacolí*” with the relative acidity of local wines. Then, we consider the main characteristics of the different kinds of *chacolí*, their evolution and changing perceptions of them. *Chacolíes* could be white, red or *rosé/ojo de gallo* [“cock’s eye”] wines. *Chacolíes* were, everywhere and every time, ones of the weakest wines available. In the 1870s, it was still possible to find white *chacolíes* with 5° of alcohol in some years. However, they were no exception to secular global trend towards higher alcohol levels in wines. The weakest current *chacolíes* contain around 9° of alcohol. *Chacolíes* were also linked with specific sociabilities and involved in various identity processes. In Northwest Spain, a tavern where these local wines were consumed with popular dishes was known as a “*Chacolí*” or “*Txakolí*”. During the last decades, *Chacolí* festivals have been created in the American and Spanish production areas. Finally, *Chacolíes* are perfect products to think about the social construction of the goodness of wines because of their particular intrinsic qualities.

Keywords: Chacolí/Txakoli, Wine, Consumption, Representation, Spain, Chile, Argentina

查科麗 (*Chacolies*) : 西班牙西北與南美的淡薄酒及強認同

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摘 要

查科麗 (*Chacolies*) 是一種廣受歡迎的淡薄葡萄酒，起源於 16 世紀初的西班牙西北部，美洲地區的歷史則可追溯至 18 世紀末或 19 世紀初。查科麗在西班牙西北部（坎塔布里亞、巴斯克地區、納瓦拉、和布爾戈斯）、智利、阿根廷（里約內格羅省）等地有悠久的生產歷

史。目前巴斯克地區生產的查科麗受到三種「原產地名稱保護制度」的規範：1989 年格塔里亞查科麗（*Getariako Txakolina*）、1994 年比斯開查科麗（*Bizkaiko Txakolina*）、和 2001 年阿拉瓦查科麗（*Arabako Txakolina*）。在討論查科麗其他面向之前，我們首先從「查科麗」的詞源來討論其複雜的內涵與概念。我們認為最可能的推論是與當地葡萄酒酸度有關的假說。其次，我們分析不同種類查科麗的共同主要特徵演變過程，與人們認知的改變。查科麗可以是白酒、紅酒、或粉紅（*rosé/ojo de gallo* [cock eye]）酒。曾經不管何時何地，查科麗都是最淡薄的葡萄酒。雖然在 1870 年代仍有酒精只有 5 度的查科麗白酒，然而，查科麗也無法抵抗世界趨勢而逐漸提高其酒精濃度，目前最淡薄的查科麗大約是 9 度。查科麗也與特定的社會性連結，參與了多重認同的建構過程。在西班牙西北部，小酒館稱之為 *Chacolí* 或 *Txakoli*，用來搭配在地常見料理。在過去幾十年中，在美洲和西班牙產區都舉辦了「查科麗」嘉年華。查科麗所具有的獨特性，提供我們一個重新思考社會如何建構所謂「好」葡萄酒的絕佳例子。

關鍵字：查科麗（*Chacolí/Txakoli*）、葡萄酒、消費、再現、西班牙／智利／阿根廷

I. Introduction

All wines are good to study, but some wines are especially good for this. *Chacolies* undoubtedly belong to this last category. Their past and present bring a lot of food for thought, not only about the ways of being in the world of the populations that produce and consume them, but also about a fundamental issue for anthropologists: the social construction of the “good wine”.

Nowadays, *chacolies* are produced in winegrowing areas located in three countries on two continents: Spain, Chile and Argentina (Figures 1 and 2). No other nations were interested in *chacolí*-making on the basis of the current knowledge. The term “*Chacolí from France*” [“*Chacolí de Francia*”] that appears in some archive documents stood for French wines that were regarded as *chacolies* in some north Spanish marketplaces, but they were not identified as “*Chacolí*” by French producers and consumers.¹ Of course, it would seem plausible that immigrants from Basque land and other parts of Northwest Spain where *chacolí*-making

¹ The term “*Chacolí from France*” appeared at least as early as the first decades of the 18th century: “*Chacolín de Francia*” [Hondarribia, 1738] (Domingo Ignacio de Egaña, *El guipuzcoano instruido en las reales cédulas, despáchos, y ordenes*, p. 96), “*Chacolí de Francia*” [Santander, 1752] (Fernando Barreda, *El chacolí santaderino en los siglos XIII al XIX*, p. 58), etc. In 1820, the wine that the captain of the schooner La Jenny omitted to declare to the Santander custom authorities was called “*Chacolí de Francia*” by them: *Diario mercantil de Cádiz*, March 3, 1820. Intended for consumption on board, this wine was in fact light wine from the region of Nantes, the home port of La Jenny: *Journal de Paris*, February 7, 1809.

was traditional, tried, with more or less success, to produce this beverage when they settled in a country we have not previously mentioned. But, until now, we have not found data that could confirm this supposition. Thanks to professor Alcides Beretta Curi, we can even write with some certainty that there never was any significant production of *chacolí* in Uruguay.²

Figure 1 Administrative provinces of Spain where *chacolí* was historically produced. Hatched, Basque Country (Autonomous Community where DOP *chacolés* are currently produced). Own elaboration.

² Personal communication, 2020.

Figure 2 Left: Administrative regions of Chile where *chacolí* was historically produced. Doñihue is located in O'Higgins region.

Right: Administrative province of Argentina with historically more notable production of *chacolí*. Own elaboration.

Academics and wine lovers who write about *chacolí* usually focus

their attention on the product of a particular vineyard region. In this text, we take the gamble that a global approach to *chacolíes* is also of interest. Beyond the local histories of *chacolí*, all of them are fascinating, there are the invention and the plural evolution of the popular cultural concept of “*Chacolí*”.

The aim of this paper is to present a synthetic panorama of the light wines named *Chacolí*, paying special attention to their identity-oriented uses. The text begins with a tentative answer to an essential but difficult question: what is a *chacolí*? Our second step will be a study of the historical destinies of various Spanish and American *chacolíes*, among which the not-to-be-missed Basque ones. Finally, we will consider *chacolí* consumption taking into account the perception of flavour of various *chacolíes*, the social construction of their goodness and the development of specific sociabilities around them.

II. What Is a *chacolí*? Wine Typology and Societies

A. The Birth of the Oenological Concept “*Chacolí*”

“*Chacolí*” is an oenological concept that appeared in the beginning of the 16th century in Northwest Spain. In the current state of knowledge, the first documents that contain it concern the coastal Basque provinces. Before January 25th 1520, the term “*chacolín* wine” [“*vino chacolín*”] was used within the framework of a court battle between the council of Begoña and two opposing parties: the tavern owners of Begoña and the lordship of

Biscay.³ In November 1520, a judicial decision in favour of María de Arranomendi, an inhabitant of Renteria, mentioned “*chacolín* wine” and cider she supplied seven years earlier to the Council, Justice and Regiment of San Sebastian.⁴ “*Chacolín* wine from the coast” was cited in the Hondarribia’s minute book in March 1542.⁵ The use of the concept of “*Chacolí*” was still confined to the coastal strip of Biscay and Gipuzkoa over the remainder of the 16th century. This concept did not seem to be widespread: only few documents from this time employed it. For example, “*chacolín* wine” was mentioned in a trade dispute resolution that concerned inhabitants of Getaria in 1570 and in a judicial answer to a fiscal problem in Lekeito in 1594.⁶ During the 17th century, the concept of “*Chacolí*” began to be used more frequently in the coastal area and to be employed further inland. In 1623, for example, a document written in Ayala (Alava) made reference to “*chacolín* local wine” [“*vino de la tierra chacolín*”].⁷ When the second volume of *Diccionario de la lengua castellana* was prepared, in 1729, the use of the substantive “*Chacolí*” was common enough in the North West of the Spanish Kingdom to justify the

³ Ana María Rivera Medina, *La civilización del viñedo en el primer Bilbao (1300-1650)*, pp. 21-2.

⁴ Archivo de la Real Chancillería de Valladolid, Registro de ejecutorias, Caja 347, 78, November 29, 1520.

⁵ Koldo Ortega in I. G., “El escudo de Hondarribia tenía racimos en una versión de 1604.”

⁶ Archivo de la Real Chancillería de Valladolid, Registro de ejecutorias, Caja 1183, 57, July 2, 1570; Archivo Municipal de Lekeitio, *Registro* 23, nº 04, 1593-1594.

⁷ Juanjo Hidalgo, et al, “Vid cultivada y silvestre en el territorio de la antigua diócesis de Valpuesta (Álava, Burgos y Cantabria, España) : un acercamiento a la historia del vino chacolí,” p. 106.

redaction of a specific entry – a text that reveals to us that the concept of “*Chacolí*” was already used in the Burgos mountains at this time.⁸ By the 1750s, the term “*Chacolí*” was more and more written in Cantabrian administrative documents.⁹ In the first half of the 19th century, a local product was called “*chacolí* wine” in the region of Pamplona.¹⁰ In parallel, the concept of “*Chacolí*” had been successfully exported to South America by some migrants from Northwest Spain.¹¹ For example, María Josefa Valenzuela, an inhabitant of Rancagua, owned “one hundred six arrobas of *chacolí*” when she died in 1829.¹² Forty years later, George Chaworth Musters tasted a wine “called *Chacolí*” that had “the muscatel flavour and bouquet of Moselle” in Rio Negro.¹³

The emergence of the concept of “*Chacolí*” in the coastal strip of Spanish Basqueland signifies an important change in the representation of wine in a region where it was produced for centuries. This innovative concept answered a need in the discourse about local wines. If people

⁸ Real Academia Española, *Diccionario de la lengua castellana*, p. 298

⁹ Fernando Barreda, *El chacolí santaderino en los siglos XIII al XIX*, p. 42.

¹⁰ Pascual Madoz, *Diccionario geográfico-estadístico-histórico de España y sus posesiones de ultramar*, p. 657.

¹¹ It is impossible to claim in the current state of knowledge that Basque migrants first brought the concept of “*chacolí*” to South America. Basque wine experts even suggested that migrants from non-Basque *chacolí*-making areas could have played an essential role in this process: Mikel Corcuera and Manolo González, *Chacolí Txakolina*, p. 188. Migration from Northwest Spain was not confined to Basque departures. The sole established fact is that parts of Basque diaspora paid special attention to *chacolí* from the 19th century onwards.

¹² Archivo Nacional de Chile, Fondo Judicial de Rancagua, Legajo 24, Pieza 8, September 29, 1829.

¹³ George Chaworth Musters, *At Home with the Patagonians*, p. 309.

widely embraced it, that was because they considered it was useful, more pertinent than the pre-existing concepts to describe a wine of their time. Once adopted, the concept of “*Chacolí*” literally erased the previous representations of local wine in the collective memory. In other words, the existence of *chacolí* became too obvious to spontaneously think that it had not always existed. Traces of such a mental process can be found as early as the 18th century. For example, the public officer who put in order the archives of Lekeitio in 1796 mentioned “*chacolí*” in his analysis of a municipal ordinance on price of wine for the year 1543, whereas the redactor of the original document had written “wine of their own harvest” [“*vino de su cosecha*”].¹⁴ Later, local scholars and gastronomes interested in *chacolí* classically went down this path and considered that the wines produced in earlier times in a place only famous in their own time for its *chacolí*, were a priori *chacolíes*. To avoid getting lost in a methodological debate, we just notice that such a process leads us to lose sight of the most important moment in the history of the *chacolí*: the moment when it received its name.

B. “*Chacolí*”: An Etymological Enigma

As the concept of “*Chacolí*” was born in Basqueland, there is sometimes a temptation to consider that *chacolí* is a very ancient Basque term, but that it was ignored in their writings by elites who used other languages over a long period of time. However, the historical reality of the linguistic

¹⁴ Archivo Municipal de Lekeitio, *Registro* 14, nº 38, 1543.

question in Basqueland casts strong doubt on this supposition. Romance languages written by the local elites were never impervious to lexical borrowing, especially in the fields of rural life and agriculture.¹⁵

The etymology of “*Chacolí*” remains obscure. Hypotheses have accumulated over the years. Even some of the less convincing of them say a lot about the identity dimension of *chacolí* consumption in Basqueland. They started to be proposed in the course of the last decades of the 19th century in the cultural context created by the emergence of a renewed Basquism. As *chacolí* was important in Basque everyday life, the argument went that the term “*Chacolí*” had to be a genuine Basque one. For example, Antonio de Trueba mentioned in *Laurak Bat* that “*Chacolí*” could be derived from “*Echacolia*” [“*Echea*” + “*Oiloa*”: “oil made at home”] or if we refine his proposal more than he did, “liquor extracted with the domestic press”.¹⁶ More recently, the local scholar Juan Uruñuela has proposed that “*Chacolí*” means “wine from the farm” and comes from complex derivation of “*Echacon*” [“neighbour of the house”].¹⁷ In the same vein, we find “*Etxeko ain*” [“enough for home”]. When an ethnographer collected this expression, it was no more than a linguistic joke made to him by an old winemaker;¹⁸ but the interest of wine-lovers and marketing experts in good stories changed it in one of the most-cited etymologies of “*Chacolí*”. The success among certain public of these

¹⁵ Manex Goyhenetche, *Histoire générale du Pays Basque. Préhistoire – Epoque Romaine – Moyen Âge*, pp. 417-22.

¹⁶ Antonio de Trueba, “Etimología del chacolí,” pp. 616-7.

¹⁷ Jesús Llona Larrauri, “Txakoli: un vino joven de muchos siglos.”

¹⁸ Antxon Aguirre Sorondo, “Del vino chacolín al txakoli,” accessed 2020/4/1.

etymological proposals is not surprising. They purport to establish a pure Basque origin of the term “*Chacolí*” and they link it with one of most important concepts in Basque culture: “*Echea*”/ “*Etxea*”.¹⁹ The same desire for Basque singularity frequently leads to prefer spelling “*Txakoli*” or using the correct Basque noun “*Txakolin*” when the wine in question is produced in a Basque province.

Some fancy hypotheses took the opposite view of this logic. Roque Barcia Martí supposed that the origin of “*Chacolí*” was the Catalan term “*Xacolí*”!²⁰ It was a major error: “*Xacolí*” is no more than a lexical borrowing with a graphic adaptation from Spanish.²¹ More contemporaneous and based on approximative scholarship, the idea that “*Chacolí*” derived from the Jewish blessing “*Baruch atah A-donay, Elo-heinu Melech Ha’Olam shehakol nihiyah bed’varo*” is an absolute nonsense:²² the blessing that corresponds to a *chacolí*-type drink is necessarily “*Baruch atah A-donay, Elo-heinu Melech Ha’Olam borei pri hagafen*” because it is indisputably a “fruit of the vine”.²³

¹⁹ *Echea/Etxea* literally means “The House” or “The Home”: Lauburu, *Etxea ou la maison basque*. As José Miguel de Barandiarán Ayerbe wrote: “The *Etxe* is land and hostel, temple and cemetery, material support, symbol and common centre of all the family members, dead or alive. It is also the community composed of its current residents and their ancestors. [...] The conceptual world of the historical Basque was organised around the *Etxe*.” (*Mitología vasca*, pp. 56-7.)

²⁰ Eduardo de Echeagaray, *Diccionario general etimológico de la Lengua española de Roque Baquia*, p. 574.

²¹ Pedro Labernia y Esteller, *Diccionari de la llengua catalana ab la correspondencia castellana y llatina*, p. 976.

²² If he is not the inventor of the *Shehakol nihiyah* hypothesis, Alberto Santana is its best publicist. He presented it in his TV broadcast *Historia de Vasconia*, 2018/7/26.

²³ *Berakhot*, 6: 1-8.

An heterogenous set of etymological assumptions looks much more interesting. No one appears indisputable among them, but they point in the same direction. Basque language would have played an important role in the genealogy of “*Chacolî*”, a word that underlines an essential intrinsic quality of the wine it designated. Their authors took into account the dynamism of Basque language, especially its capacity for borrowing.²⁴ Michel Morvan considered that “*Chacolî*” came from the Occitan “*Jacoulin*”, a term used to characterize a weak wine, more precisely a *guinguet* one.²⁵ However, this word and its variants are typical of a restricted area of Southeast France and their antiquity could be quite relative.²⁶ Consequently, one may doubt a direct borrowing of “*Jacoulin*” or “*Jangoulin*” by Basqueland inhabitants in the early 16th century. But “*Chacolî*” and “*Jacoulin*” could be related by a common root. Antonio Larrea proposed that “*Chacolî*” derived from the Castilian “*Ajolî*”, a term that contains the notion of acidity.²⁷

This idea is interesting because there is a strong probability that the concept of “*Chacolî*” was created in response to a perceived change in local wine taking into account a sensorial aspect and that wines produced further south played a major role in the awareness necessary to initiate the collective mental process that led to the creation of “*Chacolín*” by Basque

²⁴ Santiago Segura Munguía and Juan Manuel Etxebarria Ayesta, *Del latín al euskara / Latinetik euskerara*.

²⁵ Michel Morvan, *Dictionnaire étymologique basque-français-espagnol*, accessed 2020/4/1, and Frédéric Mistral, *Lou tresor dou Felibrige*, p. 54.

²⁶ Simon Jude Honnorat, *Dictionnaire Provençal-Français*, p. 466.

²⁷ Antonio Larrea, “La palabra chacolí,” p. 2653.

people. Indeed, imported wines took a new importance on Biscayan and Gipuzkoan markets at the end of 15th century and beginning of the 16th century. Among them, some were radically different from local production because their intrinsic qualities – higher alcohol concentration, more intense color, different degree of harshness or sweetness,²⁸ etc. In comparison with these products, wines such as the majority of the local ones were clearly characterised by their acidity. They became “*chacolín* wines”. Incidentally, the fact that this adjective was used early to qualify foreign wines demonstrates the weakness of the etymological hypotheses that link “*Chacolí*” with “*Etxea*”.

C. “*Chacolí*”: A Paradoxical Wine

For much of their history, *chacolies* had a paradoxical oenological status. They were indisputably wines from the technological point of view. They were always produced by fermentation of a pure grape juice obtained without adding water in the press.²⁹ In other terms, not even the worst *chacolies* were never verjuice or pomace wine.³⁰

However, their intrinsic qualities did not necessary allow *chacolies* to

²⁸ Ana María Rivera Medina, *La civilización del viñedo en el primer Bilbao (1300-1650)*, pp. 129-71.

²⁹ Pedro Fernández Niño, *Cartilla de campo y otras curiosidades, dirigidas a la enseñanza y buen éxito de un hijo*; Etniker, *Atlas etnográfico de Vasconia: la alimentación doméstica en Vasconia*.

³⁰ For the record, there was a fermented beverage named *Chacolí* that was not a grape wine! It was obtained from *guapurú* berries (*Plinia cauliflora*) in the territory conquered from Guarani people: Mariano Antonio Molas, *Descripción histórica de la antigua provincia del Paraguay*. It was certainly named by reference to the wine. This product still exists, but it is currently known under different names.

perform all the symbolic functions of a “good” wine. With low alcohol and short shelf life, *chacolés* were part of a large family of weak wines frankly depreciated by the economic elite from the very beginning of early modern times. In 1745, Manuel de Larramendi used the unflattering terms “*Vinum imbecillum*” to define *chacolí*, just like François-Antoine Pomet did decades earlier to characterise French “small wine” [*vin foible, petit vin*].³¹ One of the first English definitions of “*Chacolí*” leaves no doubt: “a poor small wine”.³² An immediate consequence of its lack of strength was the inability of *chacolí* to perform the curative function recognized in wine by classical medicine.³³ The extreme manifestation of the little *chacolí*'s ability to be regarded as a perfect pure grape juice product was its punctual exclusion from the category of potential sacramental wines. In 1698, for example, the bishop of Calahorra y la Calzada prohibited the use of weak wines “commonly called *chocolín*” to celebrate Eucharist in “mountainous and coastal places” that produced them – that is in Biscay, part of Gipuzkoa and mountains of Burgos. His argument was based on a precautionary principle: as the risk was very high that the use of one of these *chacolés* would lead to an invalid sacrament, it was preferable to celebrate the Mass with wines from “Rioja, Castilla or Navarre” because their intrinsic qualities were normally in conformity with the liturgical needs. They were at worst standard wines. For instance, the probability of

³¹ Manuel de Larramendi, *Diccionario trilingüe del castellano, Bascuence y latín*, p. 192; François Antoine Pomet, *Indiculus universalis*, p. 88. “*Vinum imbecillum*” already referred to a kind of faulty wine in Roman times: Marcus Vitruvius, *L'architecture*.

³² Hipólito San Joseph Giral del Pino, *A Dictionary Spanish and English*.

³³ Louis Viardot, “Des provinces basques et de la modification de leurs fueros,” p. 426.

using, without knowing, a product made with unripe grapes or a wine that had turned sour was much lower with them.³⁴ When the alcoholic graduation became an important criterion in the definition of valid altar wine,³⁵ *chacolíes* were more than ever before unwanted in the chalices. At the onset of the 20th century, for example, Spanish priests preferred wines that had at least 12° of alcohol, a category in which peninsular *chacolíes* exceptionally fell.

Consequently, *chacolíes* were regarded by many of those who could afford to drink “better” products as beverages that were not truly wines. In the middle of the 19th century, for instance, Ramón Joaquín Domínguez wrote: “*Chacolí*: kind of wine (like saying in parody)” [“*Chacolí: especie de vino (como si dijéramos en parodia)*”].³⁶ In 1930, an American journalist was still able to write in an article about Spanish gastronomy: “there are wines that can be hardly called such, like the Asturian and the Basque *chacoli*.”³⁷ The idea that *chacolíes* were a separate category of fermented grape juice beverage was also raised in the tax field. Because their poor alcohol content, *chacolíes* should not have been taxed as stronger wines. In 1770, the inhabitants of Llodio and Arrastaria valleys precluded paying higher tax on wine, arguing that the local *chacolí* was “not regarded as wine, but as a kind of drink a bit better than cider” [“se

³⁴ Pedro de Lepe y Dorantes, *Constituciones synodales antiguas y modernas del Obispado de Calahorra y la Calzada*, p. 258.

³⁵ Frédéric Duhart, “Bebidas con identidad. Elementos para una antropología del beber”, pp. 33-4.

³⁶ Ramón Joaquín Domínguez, *Diccionario nacional*, p. 511.

³⁷ Anonymous, “Old Spanish Sulinary Art Furnishes Pleasant Surprise to Jaded Appetites.”

conceptúa no como vino, sino como una especie de bebida poco más que la sidra”].³⁸ Such an argument was deeper than a simple taxpayers’ complaint. Even the royal administration took into account the singular nature of *chacolí* during certain periods. In the middle of the 1840s, for example, tax forms used in various Spanish provinces clearly drew a line between “Wine of all classes” and “Cider and *Chacolí*”.³⁹

Some agronomists and wine experts early extended the analogy between *chacolí* and cider beyond their low alcohol contents. In 1855, Claude Gay noted that its “bittersweet taste” made Chilean *chacolí* similar to cider.⁴⁰ A few years before, Lieutenant Gilliss noted that “in taste it [was] not unlike cider”.⁴¹ In 1877, Spanish physician Nuñez Crespo wrote in his translation of a French public hygiene manual that the composition of *chacolí* differed just a little from that of cider. He also noted that the addition of a small quantity of *chacolí* in cider could increase its alcoholic strength and aid in its preservation, without changing its nature fundamentally.⁴² For his part, a wine merchant from Alicante who declared himself “to be familiar” with Basque *chacolí*, thanks to his own drinker’s experience during two Carlist wars, alleged that some producers improved the quality of their *chacolíes*, adding apple pieces to grapes!⁴³

³⁸ Alain Huetz de Lemps, *Vignobles et vins du Nord-Ouest de l’Espagne*, p. 485.

³⁹ *Boletín oficial de la provincia de Palencia*, August, 1845; *Boletín oficial de la provincia de Santander*, August, 1845.

⁴⁰ Claude Gay, *Historia física y política de Chile. Tomo II: Agricultura*, p. 194.

⁴¹ J. M. Gilliss, *The U.S. Naval Astronomical Expedition to the Southern Hemisphere*, 2, p. 353.

⁴² Michel Lévy, *Tratado de higiene pública y privada*, 1, p. 806.

⁴³ Leandro Bernadeu y Viteri, *Tratado de vinos*, p. 33.

III. Destinies of a Large Family: *Chacolies* and PDO *Txakolinak*

A. The Emergence of PDO *Txakolinak* in Basqueland

Nowadays, an immediate distinction can be drawn between the Basque *chacolies* sent to market under Protected Designation of Origin and all the other ones. The first juridically protected designation was “*Chacolí de Getaria/Getariako Txakolina*” in 1989. Later came “*Chacolí de Vizcaya / Bizkaiko Txakolina*” (1994) and “*Chacolí de Álava / Arabako Txakolina*” (2001). For a while, the idea of a fusion in a unique PDO called “*Euskadiko Txakolina*” and composed of three sub-designations was spreading.⁴⁴ But it failed to materialise. However, the three PDO councils regularly act together in order to defend their common interests. Their most remarkable action was their battle to obtain the exclusive use of the terms “*Txakolí*”, “*Txakolina*” and “*Chacolí*”. It was a response to the renewed interest in *chacolí*-making outside the Autonomous Basque Community at the end of the first decade of the 21st century – namely, in Cantabria and Castilla-y-León.⁴⁵ The Basque PDO failed in their attempt to obtain legal recognition of “*Txakoli*” as an exclusive community trade mark from the European Union.⁴⁶ Nevertheless, Spanish and European legislation allowed them to maintain an effective monopoly of use of the

⁴⁴ Alain Huetz de Lemps, *Les vins d'Espagne*, p. 274.

⁴⁵ Sonsoles Zubeldia López, “La polémica del vino se agría.”

⁴⁶ Judgment of the General Court (Fourth Chamber), May 17, 2011.

aforementioned terms. In 2017, for example, the right to use the trade name “*Chacomena*” was denied to a winemaker established in Burgos province, because it was considered misleading.⁴⁷

The idea of obtaining a PDO label for a *chacolí* was frankly revolutionary when it emerged in the 1980s. At that time, Basque *chacolí* production had considerably declined. A large part of the vineyard acreage had disappeared and the rest was often under the threat of urban plans or agricultural reforms. Making *chacolí* usually meant producing low value-added wine as much as possible. Direct-producer hybrid vine varieties and poor operating winemaking practices affected the overall quality of local wine production. Even worse, poor wines from Catalonia were commonly sold as *chacolí* to satisfy the demand for the traditional product.⁴⁸ The pioneers of the renewal of Basque *chacolí* made a bold wager and won it by improving many aspects of *chacolí*-making.⁴⁹ De facto, the biggest strength of current PDO *txakolinak* are their specifications. Of course, their geographical origins are not negligible dimensions (Figure 3). But these wines are what they are because people accept producing them respecting certain rules. The first victory for the advocates of modern Basque *chacolí* was not only over merchants who sold foreign wine as *chacolí* but also over Basque winegrowers who produced awful *chacolí*.

⁴⁷ Marta Peciña, “La UE ratifica que la denominación ‘txakoli’ solo la pueden usar los productores vascos.”

⁴⁸ Manuel Llano Gorostiza, “El futuro del *chacolí*.”

⁴⁹ Uri Astola, “Txakolina, urteko ardoa?,” pp. 58-73.

Figure 3 Vineyard by the sea, Getaria, Guipuzkoa © Frédéric Duhart.

B. Blanco, Tinto, Ojo de Gallo: Colours of Chacolí

The *Chacolí* family was never a monolith: there are many ways to be a “light wine with a sourish taste” [*vino ligero y algo agrio*].⁵⁰ The colour of *chacolí* is variable. It could be white or red – from frankly red to intense rosé [*ojo de gallo*]. In most *chacolí*-making areas, red and white wines were historically produced. Both types of wines could be equally appreciated. However, local long-term dynamics could be more favourable for one type of *chacolíes*.

⁵⁰ Real Academia Española, *Diccionario de la lengua castellana* (1899), p. 301.

Along the Bay of Biscay, a dramatic turning point established the absolute supremacy of white ones. Castro Urdiales, for example, was famous for its “natural white” and “tasty red” *chacolíes* until the middle of the 19th century. After the crisis provoked by oidium, the renewal of local vineyard was particularly detrimental to red *chacolí* production, which became commercially irrelevant after a few decades.⁵¹ Numerous places of Gipuzkoa and Biscay suffered the same evolution of the local vine population, when the cryptogamic disease and the phylloxera did not put an end to the local wine-making tradition. Mutriku left the production of its “red *Chacoli*, which the natives [thought] equal to Bordeaux, but they [knew] no better”.⁵² In Las Encartaciones the grape variety that allowed people to obtain an honest red *chacolí* almost disappeared.⁵³ Over time, the production of red *chacolíes* continued to decline in volume. In the second half of the 2010s, approximately 95% of the *chacolíes* sent to market under PDO *Getariako Txakolina* and *Bizkaiko Txakolina* were white.⁵⁴

Further inland, the evolution of the relative importance of wines of each colour in the local production varied considerably from one *chacolí*-making area to another. In Alava, *chacolí* was “almost exclusively” obtained from the black grape variety *Graciano* at the end of the 1870s.⁵⁵ When the local vineyard began to be reconstituted after

⁵¹ Ramón Ojeda San Miguel, *El chacolí de Castro Urdiales*.

⁵² Richard Ford, *A Hand-book for Travellers in Spain*, p. 940.

⁵³ Mikel Corcuera and Manolo González, *Chacolí Txakolina*, p. 119.

⁵⁴ Data Diputación Foral de Gipuzkoa, 2014 and PDO *Bizkaiko Txakolina*, 2019.

⁵⁵ Ministerio de fomento, *Estudio sobre la exposición vinícola nacional de 1877*, p. 148.

decades of strong decline at the end of the 1980s, the choice was made to produce wines in line with the current representation of *txakoli*. During the first decade of its existence, PDO *Arabako Txakolina* only sent to market white *chacolí*. Since 2008, its offering also includes a small quantity of a red *chacolí* obtained as other current Basque ones from *Hondarribi beltza*.⁵⁶ In the regions of Pamplona and Sangüesa, *Chacolí* never ceased to be fundamentally a red wine mainly obtained from *Garnacha negra* or *Tempranillo*.⁵⁷ Farmers who also owned few white grape plants generally mixed their product with the rest of the harvest. Consequently, Navarrese white *chacolí* was still a rarity.⁵⁸ At the end of the 19th century, the most emblematic of the *chacolies* produced in the north of the province of Burgos was a pale red or intense rosé [*“clarete”*].⁵⁹ During the following decades, this *chacolí* was still occupying a preponderant place in the regional production despite a post-phylloxera evolution of the vineyard rather favourable to some white grape varieties in certain locations.⁶⁰ When an association of local small wine growers took up the challenge of revitalising the commercial production of *chacolí* in the province of Burgos, *ojo de gallo* and white wines were sent to market on equal

⁵⁶ Data Gobierno Vasco, 2008.

⁵⁷ Humberto Astibia, “A propósito del chacolí (txakolina) de las merindades navarras de Pamplona y Sangüesa,” accessed 2020/4/1.

⁵⁸ Humberto Astibia Ayerra, “Consideraciones en torno a un vino olvidado: el chacolí de Navarra,” p. 47.

⁵⁹ Diego Navarro Soler, *Teoría y práctica de la vinificación*, p. 680.

⁶⁰ Juanjo Hidalgo, et al, “Vid cultivada y silvestre en el territorio de la antigua diócesis de Valpuesta (Álava, Burgos y Cantabria, España): un acercamiento a la historia del vino chacolí,” pp. 122-5.

footing.⁶¹

In Chilean *chacolí*-producing areas, colours of wines varied in function of the local vine populations and preferences for maceration duration. In the mid-1870s, Edouard Sève summarized that rosé and white *chacolíes* were made in 13 *departamentos*, in other terms, in a space stretching out over more than 3000 km.⁶² However, the intense colour of certain rosé *chacolíes* led other persons to see them as red or, even, purplish.⁶³ In 1931, for example, a winemaker of Rengo proposed red [“*tinto*”], rosé [“*rosado*”] and white [“*torontel*”] *chacolíes*.⁶⁴ These three kinds of wines were still produced at the beginning of the 21st century.

Around the year 1900, *chacolí* was regularly described as a “white wine” in the Argentinean province of Rio Negro. However, the presence among local vine population of black and, even, colouring grape varieties strongly suggest that red or rosé *chacolíes* were also produced.⁶⁵

C. Alcohol contents of *chacolíes* throughout history

Chacolíes were, everywhere and every time, ones of the weakest wines available. Of course, it is impossible to know precisely their alcohol content before the 19th century. But all the authors who wrote about *chacolíes* giving details in the anterior period underlined their lack of “substance”. *Chacolíes* were no exception to secular global trend towards

⁶¹ Cristina Ortiz, “Miranda recoge las uvas de su primera cosecha de *chacolí*.”

⁶² Edouard Sève, *La patria chilena. Le Chili tel qu’il est*.

⁶³ Claude Gay, *Historia física y política de Chile. Tomo II: Agricultura*.

⁶⁴ Fernando Mujica, “*Chacolí* de Doñihue,” p. 241.

⁶⁵ Carlos Maria Urien and Ezio Colombo, *Geografía argentina*, p. 633.

higher alcohol levels in wines. Consequently, it is probable that the first members of this family had a very low content in alcohol. The decades 1860-1870 constitute the first period for which we are able to present an overview of Basque *chacolí* production that takes into account the alcohol content. In this time, *chacolies* generally presented a quite low content of alcohol: 6-8%, according to a chemical analysis quoted in a Basque newspaper.⁶⁶ White *chacolies* with 5° of alcohol could be even found certain years in Biscay.⁶⁷ However, few *chacolies* could stand out from the crowd, especially when the weather conditions had been favourable to the ripening of grapes. In 1862, for example, an “ordinary white *chacolí*” made the precedent year in Portugalete contained 9,75% of alcohol.⁶⁸ A century later, the strength of *chacolies* had increased a bit. It was now normal that they contained around 7-9% of alcohol.⁶⁹ Within the framework of the production under PDO, Basque *chacolies* became more alcoholic. Current specifications say that the minimum alcohol contents are: 11% (*Arabako txakolina* and *Bizkaiko txakolina* that have fermented in barrel), 10% (other *Bizkaiko txakolina*) and 9.5% (other *Arabako txakolina* and *Getariako txakolina*). In practice, these minimum levels are usually exceeded. For example, the average alcohol content of wines sent to market under PDO *Getariako txakolina* was around 11% in 2017 and

⁶⁶ Miguel Rodríguez-Ferrer, *Los Vascongados, su país, su lengua y el Príncipe L. L. Bonaparte*.

⁶⁷ Ministerio de fomento, *Estudio sobre la exposición vinícola nacional de 1877*.

⁶⁸ Francisco Balaguer y Primo, *Las industrias agrícolas*, 1, p. 489.

⁶⁹ Manuel Llano Gorostiza, “Xacolí – Chacolí – Txacolí.”

11.5% in 2018.⁷⁰ Fermented in barrel, the international award-winning 42 by *Eneko Atxa* 2015 (Biscay) and *Urtaran Cuvée* 2016 (Alava) were 13° white wines! In the north of the province of Burgos, the evolution was broadly similar. Until the efforts towards reviving the local wine-growing tradition, *chacolíes* did not exceed usually 8° of alcohol.⁷¹ Current *chacolíes* are stronger. For example, 2014's *Chacomena* and 2013's *Ch ojo de gallo* respectively contained 11% and 12.5% of alcohol.

The average alcohol content of Navarrese *chacolíes* was usually slightly higher than those of the wines produced in the westernmost provinces. However, there was some heterogeneity within the local production. The alcoholic graduations of the *chacolíes* presented by wine-growers from Navarre at the National Wine Exhibition 1877 were: 8.9°, 11.7°, 11.9°, 12.4°, 13.3° and 13.5°.⁷² The strongest of these wines were a “*chacolí de 1874*” from Pamplona and a “*chacolí de Ezcava*”. They were the results of winemaking processes more meticulous than those used in the overwhelming majority of farms. A century later, Navarrese *chacolíes* usually contained 9-11% of alcohol and some wines were still noteworthy because their higher alcohol contents: 12%, 13% and sometimes a bit more.⁷³ In Chile, *chacolíes* were also traditionally more

⁷⁰ Anonymous, “El Txakoli de Getaria, con menos uva y más graduación”; Anonymous, “El nuevo txakoli de Getaria tiene cuerpo y volumen.”

⁷¹ Ricardo Dulanto Angulo and Rafael Ocete Rubio, *Las parras de los gnomos. Epopeya del chacolí mirandés*.

⁷² Ministerio de fomento, *Estudio sobre la exposición vinícola nacional de 1877*.

⁷³ Humberto Astibia Ayerra, “Consideraciones en torno a un vino olvidado: el chacolí de Navarra,” pp. 47-8.

alcoholic than the wines from the Basque coastal provinces and their immediate neighbours. They usually contained around 11% in the early 20th century. The current production is frequently a little stronger, especially the rosé and red wines. 2019's harvest gave a 12.4° *Cacique Maravilla Chacolí rosé* (Yumbel, Biobio) and a 12.5° *Chacolí de Doñihue Polo Carreño* (O'Higgins).

Logically, certain *chacolíes* were always distinguished from the rest of the production. It could be reflected in a price difference. Some of the Navarrese *chacolíes* presented at the National Wine Exhibition 1877 were sold at more than 20 or even 30 pesetas per hectolitre; others only cost 12.5 pesetas per hectolitre.⁷⁴ Even if Spanish wine experts were very slow to pay real attention to *chacolí*, some of them early established a hierarchy among the different vineyards. In 1818, for example, a member of the Royal Madrid Economic Society wrote that the *chacolí* of Getaria was the best of Gipuzkoa.⁷⁵ Especially in Chile, some consumers were sensitive to the notion of “high-quality *chacolí*” [“*Chacolí superior*”].⁷⁶ However, specific terms were also used to qualify bad *chacolí*. In Berrioplano, it was “*Txakolintxarra*”.⁷⁷

⁷⁴ Ministerio de fomento, *Estudio sobre la exposición vinícola nacional de 1877*.

⁷⁵ Gabriel de Alonso de Herrera and alii, *Agricultura general corregida y adicionada*, p. 543.

⁷⁶ Joaquín Díaz Garcés, *Páginas chilenas: Colección de artículos, narraciones y cuentos de 1897 a 1907*, p. 350.

⁷⁷ Luis Miranda, *El euskera en el habla cotidiana de la cendea de Berrioplano*, p. 25.

IV. Drinking *Chacolí*. Tastes, Sociabilities and Identities

A. *Chacolés* as Low-class Wines

Chacolí consumption was mainly determined by necessity rather than taste for some considerable time. The majority of *chacolí* consumers drank it because it was the only wine to which they could have access. Until the end of the Ancient Regime, trade regulations even maintained a seasonal near-monopoly of *chacolí* sellers in the wine market of numerous Spanish localities that produced this light fermented beverage. It was forbidden to sell for non-medicinal use other wine than local *chacolí* while stocks lasted. In some villages and little towns, the producers successively put up for sale their *chacolí*.⁷⁸ This avoidance of competition meant for low-income retail consumers an extreme reduction in their possibilities of choice. They had to drink the available local wine! Until well into the 20th century, *chacolí* remained essentially a beverage used by farmers who were involved in a logic of self-sufficiency and by a heterogeneous population of proletarians who abandoned its consumption as soon as they were able to purchase stronger wine. During the 1870s, for example, *chacolí* was “mainly consumed by workers” in Chile.⁷⁹ A few decades later, a large majority of the costumers of the Basque taverns explicitly known as “*chacolés*” were still to be members of the popular classes.⁸⁰

⁷⁸ Etniker, *Atlas etnográfico de Vasconia: la alimentación doméstica en Vasconia*.

⁷⁹ Edouard Sève, *La patria chilena. Le Chili tel qu'il est*, 1, p. 452.

⁸⁰ Vicente Blasco Ibáñez, *El intruso*.

Chacolí was directed at such consumers even when it was exported. *Chacolies* sent from Santander to Veracruz at the end of the 18th century or to La Habana during the second half of the 19th century were not luxury beverages.⁸¹ They were only a part of the response to local demand for cheap wines.⁸²

Of course, drinking *chacolí* by necessity never prevented people from finding personal satisfaction from this. As a 1915's Chilean advertising recalls, a cheap *chacolí* could have a "exquisite flavour!"⁸³ The comments made by a Puerto Rican who visited Spain during the 1880s about the *chacolí* that a Navarrese cattle trade was drinking in the stagecoach they shared show that, in a time when wine was frequently of dubious quality, a *chacolí* made by a trustworthy person could be the most satisfactory and the healthiest option: "it was *chacolí*, pure *chacolí*, free of added water and trichina (he wanted to say fuchsin). He had bought it himself in Pamplona."⁸⁴ Logically, even the worst *chacolí* could led to behavioural disinhibition and drunkenness when it was consumed in sufficient quantity. Basques said it was able to cause "weakness in the legs" on certain feast days.⁸⁵

⁸¹ *Gazeta de México*, June 21, 1785; *Gazette nationale ou le Moniteur universel*, February 11, 1855.

⁸² Mario Trujillo Bolio, "Exportación vitícola española al mercado novohispano. Las redes de realización y sus circuitos mercantiles, 1790-1810," pp. 121-50.

⁸³ *El Mercurio*, September 15, 1915.

⁸⁴ Manuel Fernández Juncos, *De Puerto-Rico a Madrid. Estudios de viaje*, p. 107.

B. Elites and *Chacolí*-drinking: A Complex History

In *chacolí*-making areas, members of economic elite could drink this weak wine because they wanted to do. Their taste for this beverage did not necessarily imply that they regarded it as a “good” wine. It just meant that these persons who could easily access stronger wines could be interested in *chacolí*. One thing is for certain: Basque people who lived far from home did not hesitate to order *chacolí* from their relatives. In October 1829, Francisco Antonio Larraza, who worked in Cadiz, received “12 bottles of *chacolí* wine” from Bilbao.⁸⁶ In the course of the second half of the 19th century, the growing need for basqueness within the framework of the rise of the nationalist sentiment notably increased the interest of Basque elite in *chacolí*.⁸⁷ At a time when popular culture was regarded as a provider of identity markers, local weak wines became much more than potentially pleasant beverages. Products of the local humid climate, they were mainly consumed by “genuine” Basque people. They were also associated with artistic expressions like songs in the context of drinker sociabilities. In 1882, Francisco de Arechavala explained in a note about his poem *La sagardua y el chacolí* [*Cider and chacolí*] that these beverages are ones of

⁸⁵ Miguel Rodríguez-Ferrer, *Los Vascongados, su país, su lengua y el Príncipe L. L. Bonaparte*, p. 185.

⁸⁶ *Diario mercantil de Cádiz*, October 10, 1829.

⁸⁷ The creation of the Basque Nationalist Party [*Partido Nacionalista Vasco/ Euzko Alderdi Jeltzalea*] in 1895 was preceded by decades of strong affirmation of basqueness. It occurred in a context of strong industrialisation of Biscay in which references to Basque rural traditions took a special political value: Antonio Elorza, “El tema rural en los orígenes literarios del nacionalismo vasco.”

the “small details” that made the “peculiar physiognomy” of Basqueland.⁸⁸ It was no coincidence that Sabino Arana y Goiri made his foundational “speech of Larrazábal” in a *chacolí* tavern on June 3rd 1893.⁸⁹ A few months later, a journalist mentioned meals during which guests talked about politics, drank *chacolí* and sang the anthem *Gernikako Arbola*.⁹⁰ In 1895, “*txakolin blanco*” was a part of the wines served during the very symbolic Christmas dinner that the great thinker of Basque nationalism shared with members of his family in Larrínaga jail.⁹¹

In Chile, members of economic elite could also drink *chacolí* when they wanted to enjoy it. On February 16th 1817, *chacolí* from Santiago was served during the banquet offered by Bernardo O’Higgins, the newly appointed Supreme director of Chile.⁹² In the 1820s, French traveller Gabriel Lafond de Lurcy came to know rosé *chacolí* on the occasion of fine meals.⁹³ Marker of a rural way of life, *chacolí* became strongly associated with the *Fiestas Patrias* [Homeland Holidays] in the course of the 19th century. At the end of the 1910s, Rancagua newspapers published commercial advertisements that remember that *chacolí* was much more than a cheap fermented beverage during this time of the year. For instance: “*Fiestas Patrias: ¡Aprovechar!... rico chacolí especial para el 18 de*

⁸⁸ Francisco de Arechavala, *Aires del Norte*, p. 163.

⁸⁹ Sabino Arana y Goiri, *El pensamiento de Sabino Arana y Goiri a través de sus escritos*, pp. 53-8; Ana Vega Pérez de Arlucea, “El txakoli de Larrazábal.”

⁹⁰ Eusebio Blasco, “Au Pays Basque.”

⁹¹ Ana Vega Pérez de Arlucea, “El menú de Nochebuena de Sabino Arana en la cárcel.”

⁹² Vicente Pérez Rosales, *Recuerdos del pasado (1814-1860)*.

⁹³ Walter Hanisch, *El arte de cocinar de Juan Ignacio de Molina*, p. 120.

septiembre” [*Fiestas Patrias: Enjoy! Good chacolí special for September 18th*].⁹⁴

The elite’s attitude towards *chacolí* could be significantly different outside *chacolí*-making areas. When the Spanish gastronomic discourse was born at the beginning of the 19th century, the opinion that a man of good taste had to have about this wine was quickly decreed. It represented a continuation of the long tradition of depreciation, despite a slight inflection. In his loose translation of *La gastronomie* by Joseph Berchoux, José de Urcullu introduced the concept of “*chacolí*” to make comprehensible a subtle evocation of local bad wines by the French poet.⁹⁵ However, he indicated in a note that, notwithstanding its defects, *chacolí* could be useful “to refresh afternoons and dinners” in summertime. In a few words, a gourmet would have sinned by ignorance if he said that *chacolí* was a good wine but he was allowed to enjoy this beverage at appropriate moments. This concession explains why some selected *chacolies* could be proposed by Madrid quality wine sellers during the 19th century. In 1833, *chacolí* was a part of the wine offer of the grocery Del Andaluz together with champagne, wines of Bordeaux and Burgundy, sherries, etc.⁹⁶ Three decades later, *Bodega inglesa* proposed to its consumers “exquisite *chacolí*, red and white, 3 and 4 years old, from

⁹⁴ *La Semana*, September 18, 1918.

⁹⁵ José de Urcullu, *La gastronomía o placeres de la mesa. Poema por J. Berchoux*, p. 48: “Preservándoos del vino de Vizcaya, / Del flojo *chacolí* que alli se estima.” (1820); Joseph Berchoux, *La gastronomie*, p. 39: “Et des vins de mon cru constamment préservés” (1801).

⁹⁶ *Diario de avisos de Madrid*, December 9, 1833.

Epalza factory in Bilbao”.⁹⁷ The price of these *chacolies* were higher than those of the most current wines but inferior than those of the frankly renowned ones. Awards obtained by some *chacolies* in national wine exhibitions show that the disdain of oenological experts for this family of wines was not absolute during the second half of the 19th century. However, this should not create any illusions. In 1877, for instance, the eight *chacolies* that received an award only obtained the smaller prize – *Diploma de mención*.⁹⁸ Not only that, *chacolies* did not compete with other wines: they were assessed as *chacolies*. Their participation in the competition did not even represent a recognition of their full membership in the wine family: ciders and vinegars were also assessed! In fact, wine expert positions were in perfect harmony with the now classic gastronomic opinion about *chacolies*. They were broadly uninteresting wines, but the best of them could be a useful “summer drink” [*bebida de verano*].⁹⁹ Until the earlier successes of contemporaneous *txakolinak*, the non-local opinion about *chacolies* of Northern Spain changed very little. The development of the gastronomic tourism just added the ideas that *chacolies* married perfectly with certain Basque dishes and that they were better when they were drunk “*in situ*”.¹⁰⁰

⁹⁷ *La Correspondencia de España. Diario universal de noticias*, December 18, 1863.

⁹⁸ Distribution of the awarded *chacolies* among the producing areas: Navarre (3), Burgos (2), Biscay (2) and Guipuzkoa (1).

⁹⁹ Ministerio de fomento, *Estudio sobre la exposición vinícola nacional de 1877*, p. 183.

¹⁰⁰ “El chacolí de Vizcaya.”

C. Past and Present Sociabilities of *chacolí*-drinking

Chacolí was traditionally consumed in a domestic environment or in taverns. Basque gastronomic societies [*txokoak*] also became places where this local wine could frequently be served. They were ones of the last bastions of *chacolí* consumption at the end of the 20th century and played an important role in the promotion process of PDO *txakolinak* a few years later.¹⁰¹ As the superb *Despachando chacolí* by Navarrese painter Javier Ciga Echandi recalls, taverns that sold *chacolí* were still to be generally rustic and little furnished places at the beginning of the 20th century.¹⁰² They were commonly called *chacolíes* throughout Spanish *chacolí*-making region. In the centre of Miranda del Ebro, for example, there were *Chacolí Chamorro* and *Chacolí Limaco*.¹⁰³ In the course of the second half of the 19th century, the Sunday attendance of *chacolíes* located in immediate proximity of the city became an essential practice of sociability among Bilbao workers. There were as many as 44 *chacolíes* in Begoña, 13 in Baracaldo, 11 in Abando or Portugalete, 10 in Deusto, etc. Groups of friends came to these places not only to drink weak wine and to eat dishes such as cod in *pil pil* sauce, pork tenderloin with chili peppers, lamb in sauce, beef tripe stew, blood sausage or pilchards, but also to bowl, to play

¹⁰¹ Etniker, *Atlas etnográfico de Vasconia: la alimentación doméstica en Vasconia*. During the year 2007, for instance, the department of Agriculture of Basque government organised numerous *txakoli* tasting session in gastronomic societies.

¹⁰² Humberto Astibia, “Nuevos datos sobre los chacolís (txakolinak) de la Alta Navarra y de Araba y el ámbito territorial del chacolí,” accessed 2020/4/1.

¹⁰³ Cristina Ortíz, “El legado del chacolí mirandés.”

cards, to sing, to dance, etc.¹⁰⁴ The atmosphere of these popular recreational places was so colourful from a bourgeois point of view that postcards showing it were published (Figures 4 and 5). *Chacolies* disappeared during the second half of the 20th century. Beautiful symbol, the *Txakolí* of Artxanda is currently a prestigious restaurant where *txakolí* is not systematically served! Its immediate neighbours, *Txakoli Simón* and *Txakoli Ballano* offer a more traditional cuisine, but their wine lists are too rich to remember the past.

Figure 4 Effects of *chacolí*, postcard, 1900s.

¹⁰⁴ Luis Haranburu Altuna, *Historia de la alimentación y de la cocina en el País vasco*.

Figure 5 A *chacolí* in Bilbao, postcard, 1900s.

Chacolí festivals are special opportunities for sociability around this light wine. Created in 1975, the *Fiesta del chacolí* of Doñihue was certainly the first one.¹⁰⁵ In 1992, the *Fiesta Provincial del Vino Chacolí* was established in Guardia Mitre.¹⁰⁶ Numerous festivals were created during the last three decades in Basqueland. The concept of the Day of *Chacolí* [*Txakoli Eguna*] was widely exploited in the territories of the three PDO. These events are generally organised at the end of the winter or during spring to spotlight the new vintage. A Harvest Festival [*Fiesta de la vendimia*] has been celebrated since 2001 in Zarautz (Gipuzkoa) and

¹⁰⁵ Pablo Lacoste et al, “Vinos típicos de Chile: ascenso y declinación del chacolí (1810-2015).”

¹⁰⁶ Law n 2518, Rio Negro Province.

2015 in Balmaseda (Biscay). In Burgos, a Day of *Chacolí* [*Día del chacolí*] has been organised within the framework of the Valle de Mena craft festival since 2006. Of course, it is devoted to the celebration of the local wines and not of the Basque ones.¹⁰⁷ All these events have their specificities but they fundamentally testify of efforts to involve the cultural marker *chacolí* in local identity dynamics and to complete the construction of the local wine authenticity by the mobilization of local community.

V. Conclusion

Past and present, a *chacolí* is basically defined by a single trait: it is a light wine. During a long time, this characteristic condemned the *chacolí* to be primarily a vulgar beverage, a kind of wine that was generally consumed for lack of access to a better one, if not to a real one. The association of *chacolí* with cider to form a category distinct from “wines” in some Spanish tax forms sheds light on this social representation. In a country where stronger wines were regarded as the top beverages, *chacolí* could be literally relegated to the status of a cider made with grapes! Wherever *chacolí* was produced or imported, it was above all drunk by the lower classes. Of course, members of the economic elite could drink it because they wanted to; but *chacolí* did not become a prestigious wine during this long period. For this reason, *chacolí* and the sociability linked with its

¹⁰⁷ Anonymous, “El chacolí de Mena sobrevive gracias a la vieja guardia.”

consumption became emblematic pieces of popular culture and strong identity markers in most regions of Northwest Spain, Central Chile and South Argentina traditionally interested in its production.

From the 19th century, the identity value of *chacolí* was enough to stimulate a romantic nationalist consumption within certain upper-class circles both in Basqueland and South America. Travellers and tourists also early became interested in tasting *chacolí* because they saw it as an original local beverage and the public places where it was served as truly picturesque ones. Some of these less traditional *chacolí* drinkers could sensorially enjoy their meeting with this singular wine. However, even the more enthusiastic of them did not consider *chacolí* as a potential top wine. In fact, their positive appreciation of its intrinsic qualities had a lot to do with the fact that *chacolí* was the opposite of a sophisticated product, a symbolic concentrate of rural non-elite culture.

Complex results of a subtle combination of natural factors and applications of know-how, the intrinsic qualities of *chacolíes* could logically be different, depending the producers, even in a quite small vineyard area. Everywhere, *chacolí* consumers could interpret them according to the criteria of their own social group: the wine of the year could be better or worse than that of the previous year, the *chacolí* from one house could taste good or bad, etc. However, until well into the 20th century, their opinions about *chacolíes'* quality generally had very little impact on their practices of consumption because the overwhelming majority of them really had no choice about the *chacolí* they drank. Those who produced *chacolí* for self-consumption had to drink it even if it was

less tasty than previous year, those who bought *chacolí* did not have access to a broad range of products, etc. In Northwest Spain and America, few actors of wine industry early tried to promote what they perceived as the best *chacolies*. But their action had a limited impact and *chacolí* globally remained an unattractive product, mostly drunk for lack of something better. As a testament to this, when their purchasing power increased sufficiently, the lower classes did not look for better *chacolí*, but they bought the best “real” wine they could afford.

At the beginning of the last quarter of the 20th century, *chacolí* appeared to be condemned to survive, at best, as a relic of the “world we have lost”¹⁰⁸ ... if it did not vanish quickly. But some Basque winegrowers made the bet of drastically improving *chacolí* making in the 1980s. It was a fundamental turning-point in the history of this family of wines: thank to their efforts and, of course, to a favourable evolution of the global wine-lover culture, the glass ceiling that prevented *chacolí* to become a fine wine was definitely broken in a few decades. At the end of the 2010s, Basque PDO *chacolies* were ones of the most fashionable wines in the world according to articles published in the international press and contest results.¹⁰⁹

Basque innovators did not only offer to their *txakoli* a commercial and gastronomic status that no *chacolí* previously obtained, but they also

¹⁰⁸ Peter Laslett, *The World We Have Lost: England before the Industrial Age*.

¹⁰⁹ For instance: Michael Austin, “Txakoli: Spain’s Instantly Likable Wine is Fun, Fizzy and Food-friendly”; Julián Méndez, “El txakoli ‘42 by Eneko Atxa’, elegido mejor vino blanco del mundo.”

substantially improved its identity value. After it became a fine wine, *txakoli* was more and more used as an emblem of basqueness both by food processors and artists.¹¹⁰ In other words, it became a much more visible emblem.

The success and the increased visibility of the Basque PDO *chacolies* regenerated interest in this family of wines in most regions where it was traditionally produced. Everywhere, as in Gipuzkoa, Biscay and Alava, motivations of actors who decided to relaunch local *chacolí*-making were a subtle mix of economic interests, concerns for local heritage and politics. In the late 2000s, the attempt by the regulatory councils of the three Basque PDO *chacolies* to obtain an exclusive use of the “*txakoli* brand” to the detriment of their neighbours to Cantabria and Burgos perfectly showed the complexity of this dynamics. Some only considered *txakoli* in business terms, other ones underlined historical realities, politicians acted with a keen sense of national cohesion or, on the contrary, exclusively taking into account the interest of their autonomous community, etc. A decade after the beginning of this “battle of *Txakoli*”, the only *chacolies* under PDO are still the three Basque ones. However, a winemaker sells bottles of a wine named *Ch* and tourists can travel along a “Road of *Chacolí*” in the Province of Burgos. Proyecto Matoblanco produces a wine that discretely and surely assumes its identity of *chacolí santaderino*.

¹¹⁰ For instance, the confectioner Gorrotxategi created a chocolate filled with *txakoli* ganache: Frédéric Duhart, *Le chocolat au Pays Basque (XVII^e-XXI^e siècle)*, p. 101. *Txakoli* appears in the Emilio Martínez-Lázaro’s film *Eight Basque Surnames* [original title: *Ocho apellidos vascos*], 2014.

People are working on the creation of a DO *Chacolí de Doñihue* in Chile and the Argentinean municipality of Guardia Mitre is prouder than ever of its *chacolí*.¹¹¹

All of these *chacolíes* are legitimate and able to interest wine-lovers. Are they potential competitors? Answering this question is in fact revealing of an intimate view on wine industry. For people who sincerely think that the origin of a wine is important in the construction of its identity because the existence of a complex alchemy between grape-variety, effect of *terroir* or know-how factors, etc, the *chacolíes* from different origins are necessarily distinct products. In consequence, they cannot be in direct competition, except if the consumers are not able to appreciate the difference between them. To seriously consider that a *chacolí* from Burgos can be a real long-term competitor of a Biscayan one without looking at the wine-lovers as an uneducable crowd of dummies, it is necessary to think that they can only be differentiated by their names and the results of marketing decisions... Both answers say a lot about the contemporary wine industry: “In *Chacolí* lies the truth”.

¹¹¹ Cristóbal de Castillo Camus, “Saber-hacer chacoli. Registro y documentación de la producción del vino chacoli de Doñihue para su reconocimiento como Denominación de Origen,” pp. 56-9. Brochure *Ruta del chacolí burgales*, Diputación de Burgos, 2016. The wine *Ch* is produced by Bodegas Término de Miranda SL, Miranda del Ebro. Proyecto Matoblanco, Cueto. Bunches of red grapes are represented on the arms of the municipality of Guardia Mitre (year of creation: 2018).

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